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Emerging Paradigm of Employees' Involvement in Decision Making and Organizational Effectiveness: Further Evidence from Nigerian Manufacturing Firms

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ABSTRACT

This study explored employees' involvement in decision making and organizational effectiveness of manufacturing firms. The cross-sectional survey research design was employed. Data were elicited from the middle and lower level employees of manufacturing firms registered under the Manufacturing Association of Nigeria (M.A.N.), Edo/Delta Chapter retrieved as at 31st October, 2021. For the purpose of the research, ten firms were selected with a total staff population of 1,839. Taro Yamane's formula was used in arriving at a sample of 329 employees and 216 responses retrieved were analyzed using the simple percentage, mean statistics, and hypotheses tested with linear regression after multicollinearity test and correlation matrix revealed no collinearity problem. Results of hypotheses tested showed that employees' involvement in decision making has significant effect on organizational productivity, organizational adaptability, and organizational flexibility. Accordingly, the study recommended that the top management level of manufacturing firms should see the need to constantly involve the middle and lower level employees in their decision making processes whether directly or through advisory participation, to continually gain more effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Employees' involvement in decision making (hereafter EIDM) means the extent to which employees are permitted to take part in organizational decision-making processes (Dede, 2019). According to Mambula, Francis and Zirra (2021), several ways in which an organization permits EIDM include; direct participation (whether short, moderate or long term), representation at the board level, through quality circles, and consultation (or advisory). EIDM has been discussed in literature to bring about increased motivation among employees, improved organizational performance, and overall firm's growth (Kim, Mac-Duffie & Pil, 2010).

However, some studies (Locke & Schweiger, 1997, Obiekwe, Zeb-Obipi & Ejo-Orusa, 2019) have contrary opinions on the desirability of including employees in decision making at the managerial level. They identified some reasons to include the fright of disclosing vital business strategies, and the cost associated with involving employees. Notwithstanding, a handful of organizations have recognized that EIDM is a paramount step to boost employees' commitment towards their job tasks aimed at sustaining organizational effectiveness. Hence, involving employees adds to the overall well-being of organizations (Management Study Guide [MSG], 2016).

Organizational effectiveness (OE) is an extensive concept that measures extent of achievement of various firms' objectives (Amah & Ahiauzu, 2013). Evidence abounds on the nexus between EIDM and OE. Some of these studies have associated employees' involvement with increased commitment to workplace tasks (Myilswamy & Gayatri, 2014), job satisfaction (Mohsen & Sharif, 2020), profitability (Daniel, 2019), and productivity (Mambula et al., 2021). But in general, there are still mixed submissions

on the outcome of EIDM on overall organizational effectiveness. While studies such as those of Kataria et al (2013) and Saeed (2016) found that employees' involvement has a positive effect on organizational effectiveness, others, such as Daniel (2019) revealed that if there is no reform in work tasks, involving employees can result in a negative outcome such as conflict in work roles.

In the Nigerian setting, EIDM and organizational effectiveness of manufacturing firms has not been addressed holistically. Very scanty empirical literature on OE exists in the sector. Preliminary observation has shown that the non-involvement of employees when taking organizational decisions especially those that affect them results in lack of commitment towards their job tasks which invariably impact on organizational success. Dissatisfaction has also been observed to arise from decisions taken horizontally by top management, which has led to negative reactions by employees such as embarking on strikes, industrial wars, employees' anxieties and having reduced interest in their jobs (Ojokuku & Sajuyigbe, 2014, Oyebamiji, 2018).

On this note, this study seeks to examine, from the context of Nigerian manufacturing firms, EIDM and OE, paying attention to the different forms of EIDM in these firms at the operational and tactical levels as well as how their involvement impact on three aspects of OE (productivity, adaptability and flexibility). Specifically, it is to: (i) ascertain whether EIDM has any significant effect on organizational productivity as a dimension of OE, (ii) investigate the extent to which EIDM influences organizational adaptability as a dimension of OE; and to (iii) ascertain whether EIDM can influence organizational flexibility as a dimension of OE. This study is significant

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as it provides new insights on the subject matter from the manufacturing sector of an emerging economy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employees' Involvement in Decision Making

Employee involvement has been used in the literature interchangeably with employee participation, job involvement, job engagement, employee engagement, and employee voice (Appelbaum, Louis, Makarenko, Saluja, Meleshko & Kulbashian, 2013; Shaed, Zainol, Yusof & Bahrin, 2018). According to Nachiket (2014) employees' involvement is a series of activities planned out to elicit the support, encouragement, indulgence and optimum contribution of employees at all levels in an organization so as to bring about unceasing improvement towards the attainment of organizational goals. Dede (2019) referred to it as the act of top level management sharing its influence with employees of other levels who are hierarchically unequal. And as added by Mambula et al (2021), it also explains the latitude to which an employer gives room for employees to give their suggestions concerning organizational decisions and the extent to which these suggestions are implemented. With this, employees share their opinions and knowledge with their co-workers and management, thereby fostering employer-employee, employee-employee and manager-employee relationships.

Commenting on the essence of EIDM, Obiekwe et al (2019) emphasized that the need for involvement stems from the understanding that two good heads are better than one. A modest question or suggestion from a low level employee can help management in their development of innovative practices, reduce unnecessary expenses or have clue about issues that can be anticipated and ways they can be dealt with. This therefore implies that the benefits associated with involving employees at decision levels cannot be undermined.

Kuye and Sulaimon (2011) highlighted three benefits associated with EIDM to include improved value in decisions taken, amplified employees' commitment, and approval of decisions through a sense of ownership. According to Myilswamy and Gayatri (2014), involved employees tend to be more engaged, show more loyalty, and display positive attitudes towards their job tasks, the organization's beliefs, goals and objectives. This invariably leads to enhanced performance. As such, an undeniable connection exists between EIDM and firm's effectiveness.

Notwithstanding the positive things that have been said about involving lower and middle level employees in decision making, the extent of this involvement is faced with a myriad of challenges. The first of such barriers is the negative attitude of those at the top management level towards employee involvement. For instance, most managers get the feeling that involving their subordinates when taking decisions lessen their hierarchical authority, and as such, take steps to ensure that any move made by management to include employees in decisions is averted.

Another challenge that limits EIDM is management's dread of revealing strategic business ideas by employees. This happens when management lacks trust in its employees not to disclose business strategies to their rivals whether intentionally or unintentionally. Other challenges include inadequate skilled manpower, costs involved in such programmes, insufficient support from top management, employees' reluctance to be involved, among others.

Forms of Employees' Involvement in Decision Making

Different authors have posited several methods to get employees involved in organization's decision making. For example, earlier studies (such as Levine & Tyson, 1990) acknowledged two types of involvement as consultative and substantive. Others have included partial participation, employees' ownership face-to-face, collective, pseudo and paternalistic involvement (Sagie & Ayeon, 2003), committee affiliation (Apostolou, 2000), empowerment, team positioning, and skill advancement (Lawler & Mohman, 1989), and joint responsibility (Khattak, Iqbal & Khattak, 2013). However, in more recent literature, Amah and Ahiazu (2013) grouped these methods into two: formal and informal participation. While the formal has to do with involving employees via recognized structure put in place, the informal incorporates all unplanned ways by which employees are involved.

Tizazu (2014) submits that employees' involvement can either be direct or indirect (advisory). In addition, Shaed et al (2018) indicated three mechanisms of EIDM to include

- (i) information sharing,
- (ii) consultative involvement, and
- (iii) democratic/delegative involvement.

In the same vein, Asokk, Gudda, Bhati and Vanishree (2021) identified six ways through which management could involve employees. They include: involvement in work decisions, giving some level of authority to employees, deploying them in representative positions, consulting their opinions / suggestions, engaging them casually and making them take part in rare short-term management activities. Further explanation of the forms of employee's participation is done using Tizazu (2014) classification.

Direct Participation

The direct participation, according to Tizazu (2014), can be consultative or deliberate and denotes employees' instant communication, collaboration and co-decision making with top level management. Employees' direct participation could be in the form of team meetings, suggestion systems, in-house journals, etc. Employees participating directly in decision making could be about daily operations or activities outside work operations such as volunteering. Subordinates' direct participation is determined by the nature and course of the decision and

could be partitioned into downward communication (a system where employees are sent written memos, journals, texts, or training videos enlightening them on decisions to be made) and upward problem-solving (a system put in place by top management to tap into subordinates' personal or group knowledge on departmental practices and operations).

Similarly, Keller and Werner (2011) opined that employees' direct participation happens when they share their concerns or suggestions on top level matters; and as such, it requires that they partake, speak up for themselves concerning work and/or work-related issues. In support of this view, Mambula et al (2021) noted that one major feature that makes the direct participation of subordinates unique is the fact that they jointly make decisions with their superiors. However, the study spotted that this level of participation has resulted in low morale and decreased productivity since employees are mostly interested in only decisions that concern them. Also, on the part of the employees, they are encouraged to have the right knowledge and competence in matters that their suggestions are needed to ensure a swift and fruitful outcome from the participative process.

Advisory Participation

Asokk et al (2021) described this form of involvement as the process of top management level including a group of subordinates from different departments in an organization who also speak publicly about approaches that could be adopted to improve organizational efficiency and deal with technological concerns. An example is the consultation of knowledgeable and competent employee who is a professional in a particular aspect of a firm's operation. Thus, advisory involvement can be achieved through the use of accuracy circles.

Formation of committees is also an example of advisory participation of subordinates (Ugwu, Okoroji & Chukwu, 2019). It is common in situations whereby issues have been constantly reported to management about a particular matter and investigative panel is set up among the subordinates to find out the causes and proffer possible solutions to the issues. A committee report is mostly prepared and submitted by the employee heading such committee and a suggested decision to be taken is put before the management, which is mostly accepted.

Organizational Effectiveness

The issue of performance is constantly being addressed in businesses especially in manufacturing firms without due recourse to what constitutes firms' effectiveness. The manufacturing industry is a prospective tool for transformation, a creator of employment, and an initiator of progressive spill-over impact (Kuye & Sulaimon, 2011). Besides, manufacturing sector has impacted greatly on the effective transformation of some economies that have maintained a constant increase in their per-capita income (Soderbom & Teal, 2012). This proves

that attention should be paid to manufacturing and the elements that could nurture its progress.

Rahimi and Noruzi (2011) have opined that it is hard to define exactly what an organizational effectiveness entails because it is a multidimensional construct used to determine the extent to which an organization attains its success and it contains several elements used to measure organizational performance (Lee & Choi, 2003). Implicitly, effectiveness is one of the deep-sought dependent variables of interest to both management and subordinates, and as such, varies from one organization to another.

Amah and Ahiazu (2013) suggested two ways of evaluating OE; the traditional and modern approaches. The former includes approaches like the goal approach, which is centered on assessing the desired outputs from employees versus the actual employees' outputs; while the latter include profitability, which is a reflection of overall performance.

Earlier studies such as Daft (1998) have outlined two main ways of measuring organizational effectiveness to include the traditional and contemporary approaches. The traditional has to do with: (i) goal approach, (ii) system resource approach, and (iii) internal process approach. The contemporary approach deals with productivity, adaptability, and flexibility. The latter has been noted by most scholars to be the most widely adopted for measuring OE (Sharma & Samantara, 1995; Kataria, Rastogi & Garg, 2013).

Sharma and Samantara (1995), Kataria, Garg and Rastogi (2013) opined that three variables have proven to be the most extensively used for evaluating organizational effectiveness. These variables are (i) productivity (which comprises the quality and quantity of employees' output, product or service) (ii) adaptability (which measures how employees and the entire organization adjust to situational issues, whether anticipated or existing), and (iii) flexibility (which measures how structures in an organization are maintained). This present study uses these dimensions.

To permit empirical investigation of the study's objectives, the following hypotheses are formulated:

1. EIDM has no significant effect on organizational productivity.
2. EIDM does not significantly influence organizational adaptability.
3. EIDM has no significant impact on organizational flexibility.

Conceptual Model of the Study

The conceptual model demonstrates the connection between the dependent variable (OE) and the independent variable (EIDM). The sub-independent variables are: employees' direct participation and advisory involvement while the sub-dependent variables are organizational productivity, level of adaptability and flexibility. It is illustrated that EIDM is presumed to have an influence on the OE of manufacturing firms.

Figure 2: Employees' Involvement and Organizational Effectiveness

Source: Authors' Conceptualization of EIDM and Organizational Effectiveness of Manufacturing Firms.

Empirical Review on EIDM and Organizational Effectiveness

A review of studies on EIDM in various sectors is necessary and this is done in a chronological order. Studies from the international scene are reviewed first followed by works on the local scene. Kataria et al (2013) examined employees' engagement in relation to OE in the Indian information technology sector. A retrospective analysis was done of existing theoretical and empirical research studies to support the interrelationship among employees' engagement, organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and organizational effectiveness. Findings indicated that employees' engagement has the potentials to drive OCB and higher levels of OCB augment organizational effectiveness. Thus, it was established that a significant relationship exists among organizational effectiveness, OCB, and employees' engagement.

In the banking sector, Dajani (2015) examined the impact of employees' engagement on job performance and organizational commitment using 245 public and private banks' employees in Egypt. The results indicated that leadership and organizational justice were significant drivers of employees' engagement. Employees' engagement significantly impact job performance, but less on organizational commitment.

Saeed (2016) assessed the impact of employees' involvement on organizational effectiveness of Islamic University, Bahawalpur, Pakistan using 242 teachers conveniently selected. The regression analysis revealed significant and positive relationships between the independent variables (team orientation, employee empowerment, and capability development) and OE.

Shrestha (2019) examined employees' engagement and performance of Nepalese public enterprises using both the administrative and technical employees of Tribhuvan University (TU), Nepal. The survey method was used which involved 150 employees and found employees' engagement to positively relate with performance if moderated by workforce diversity.

Mohsen and Sharif (2020) examined the effect of EIDM on job satisfaction in Afghanistan International Bank. One hundred and twenty eight (128) bankers were selected using the total enumeration sampling technique. The results of the regression analysis showed that EIDM

has a positive effect on job satisfaction. The results also showed that employees' commitment, organizational structure, leader behavior, and the workplace are among the factors that produce positive impact on participation while education level has no relationship with participation.

More recently, Asokk et al (2021) investigated EIDM and organizational performance using a survey of 130 private workers and administrators. The ANOVA results indicated that EIDM positively affect overall productivity and that staff's participation also has positive consequences on management's performance.

In Nigeria, Ojokuku and Sajuyigbe (2014) surveyed whether EIDM influences performance of selected SMEs in Lagos. Data were sourced from 129 employees and 27 owner/managers using questionnaire. The results showed that EIDM has significant positive influence on performance. Oyebamiji (2018) investigated the influence of EIDM on organizational performance using 205 respondents from Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Ogbomosho, Oyo State. The study reported that direct participation had significant positive impact on performance. The findings also revealed low extent of employees' involvement due to the unwillingness of the management to share decision-making processes with the subordinates.

Ugwu et al (2019) examined the relationship between participative decision making and employees' performance in the Hospitality Industry using selected hotels in Owerri, Imo State. Participative decision making was partitioned into leader behaviour and organizational structure while employees' performance was proxied by employees' job satisfaction and commitment. Questionnaire was administered to 92 supervisors and managers of five randomly selected hotels. The correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between the explained and explanatory variables.

Dede (2019) explored the relationship between EIDM and organizational productivity in Cross River State Board of Internal Revenue, Calabar. Primary data was obtained from 80 respondents using questionnaire. Findings from the study indicated that participation makes decision implementation easier, creates a good working environment, increases commitment and satisfaction on decisions taken, and also increases employees' morale since they feel recognized. Consequently, there is improved productivity.

Ezeanolue and Ezeanyim (2020) investigated employees' participation and organizational productivity in manufacturing establishments in South-East, Nigeria. The study's population was 2, 416 employees while a sample of 470 was selected using Borg and Gall's (1973) statistical formula. The study submitted that employees' consultation, involvement, and commitment positively affect organizational productivity. However, the study did not determine the impact these variables have on firms' effectiveness.

Mambula et al (2021) explored the effect of EIDM on

organizational productivity of Access Bank in Yola, Adamawa State. Purposive sampling was used to pick 50 employees. The finding showed that high level of employees' involvement is positively linked with bank's productivity since creativity and innovation are promoted by involving employees in decision-making processes.

Theoretical Framework

Several theories have been propounded on the possible connections between employees and the organization. These theories include the human capital theory (postulated by Schultz in 1961 and developed by Gary Becker in 1964 to explain how instructing valuable skills and knowledge on subordinates would improve their productivity), self-determination theory (formally made known in mid 1980s by Deci and Ryan to describe the tactics that management can use to motivate subordinates), the social exchange theory (SET) (developed by Blau in 1964 to explain how subordinates will be encouraged to give more to their jobs if there is a balanced system of exchange with management), among others.

However, this study has its roots on the goal setting theory (GST), which was introduced by Edwin Locke in 1968. This theory states that persons are encouraged to give in their best towards achieving the objectives of a course which they set for themselves or they are a part of. By inclusion in a process, an individual recognizes what the process entails and will go all out to see the aims of that process actualized. In its application, the goal setting theory helps to explain how an organization can gain effectiveness in its processes and outcomes if it involves its employees at all levels (whether top, middle or lower) in all its decisions linked with its operations. Therefore, this study assumes that if the middle and lower level employees of manufacturing firms are involved in decision making (either through direct participation, or advisory involvement), it will result in improved tasks results (productivity), better situational adjustments (adaptability) and higher flexibility.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study adopted the cross-sectional survey design. The population comprises all the middle and lower level employees of the entire thirty manufacturing firms registered under the Manufacturing Association of Nigeria (M.A.N.), Edo/Delta State Chapter retrieved as at 31st October, 2021. But for purposes of this research, ten firms (with employees totaling 1,839) dispersed around major regions of the States were used from where a sample size of 329 employees determined using Taro Yamane framework was selected. Descriptive and inferential statistical tools were used to conduct the data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the responses while regression analysis was used for hypotheses testing. The alpha level of significance for the test was set at 5%. Multicollinearity test and correlation matrix were computed and no collinearity problem was found.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The instrument used was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Employee Involvement in Decision Making and Organizational Effectiveness Questionnaire (EIDMOEQ)". It was divided into three sections: Part I was on the respondents' personal data; Part II contained sixteen (16) items sectioned under the two sub-independent variables (direct participation and advisory involvement) to measure the extent of their application in firms; and Part III raised fifteen (15) items on organizational OE.

To measure the extent to which employees from the middle and lower levels of the firms are involved in decision making under the different sections, the scale developed by Barringer and Bluedorn (1999) was adapted which ranged from "1 for no involvement to 5 for substantial involvement" while the six point Likert scale of 1 for Don't Know to 6 for Very Effective, was adopted to measure the extent of the firms' effectiveness using three dimensions (productivity, adaptability, and flexibility).

Instrument's Reliability

To ensure the instrument's reliability, the Cronbach alpha method of reliability was used to ascertain the consistency of the instrument's constructs and scales. The independent variable had Cronbach alpha value of 0.971 while the dependent variable had 0.973. Thus, the results showed that the instrument is reliable since all the values are greater than 0.70 (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysis of Responses

In all, a total of 329 copies of structured questionnaire were administered but only 216 were returned without errors and considered usable for further data analysis indicating a 66% response rate. This is above the benchmark suggested by Oghuvbu (2010) who noted that 60% and above response rate is statistically convenient for further analysis and can be reliably used. Most of the respondents have worked in their firms for between 1-10years (N=187) while the lower level employees that participated in the study is 162.

To measure the extent of employees' involvement in the different aspects of decision making, the mean scores of all the sub-section's items are summed and averaged to ascertain the aggregate mean which is matched against the criterion mean of 3.00. If the aggregate mean score is greater than the criterion mean (>3.00), it indicates that the extent of the employees' involvement is high while if it is less than the criterion mean (<3.00), it depicts that the employees' involvement is low.

Table 1 shows that with aggregate means of 1.39 and 2.31 respectively, which are lesser than the criterion mean of 3.00, the extent of involvement, whether through direct participation or advisory involvement, is low. However, the extent to which the employees partake in decisions

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of EIDM

S/N	Employees' Involvement in Decision Making	N	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.
	(I) Direct Participation			
1	Organizational planning decisions	216	1.24	.692
2	Decisions on tactical operations	216	1.64	.904
3	Decisions on firm's strategic policies	216	1.53	.925
4	Decision on the procurement of firm's resources	216	1.67	.778
5	Decisions on new innovations	216	1.25	.747
6	Recruitment and firing decisions	216	1.12	.447
7	Production decisions	216	1.49	1.034
8	Decisions regarding sales	216	1.33	.851
9	Departmental practices and operations	216	1.24	.585
	Aggregate Mean	1.39		
	Criterion Mean	3.00		
S/N	(I) Direct Participation	N	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.
10	Decisions on technological concerns	216	2.31	.910
11	Problem-solving options	216	2.67	1.343
12	Decisions on workers' assessment	216	1.16	.476
13	Evaluation of new trends in manufacturing industry	216	3.00	1.383
14	Review of new regulations and staff policies	216	1.18	.528
15	Firm's in-house practices	216	3.26	.964
16	Decisions on new markets	216	2.58	1.385
	Aggregate Mean	2.31		
	Criterion Mean	3.00		

Authors' computation

regarding evaluation of new trends in manufacturing industry and firms' in-house practices are high as indicated by their mean scores of 3.00 and 3.26 respectively. The standard deviation values are low, symptomatic of individual values clustering around the mean. To measure OE, the mean scores of all the sub-sections' items are summed and averaged to ascertain the aggregate

mean which is matched against the criterion mean of 3.50. If the aggregate mean score is greater than the criterion mean (>3.50), it indicates that the firms are very effective in their organizational effectiveness while if it is less than the criterion mean (<3.50), it depicts that the firms are very ineffective.

Table 2 reveals aggregate mean scores of 4.58, 4.39

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of OE

S/N	Organizational Effectiveness	N	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.
	(A) Firm's Productivity			
1	Raw materials for manufacturing	216	4.07	1.573
2	Manufacturing processes	216	4.17	1.427
3	Number of units produced	216	4.79	1.693
4	Employees' hours of operations	216	4.38	1.589
5	Technical knowledge	216	5.51	.960
	Aggregate Mean	4.58		
	Criterion Mean	3.50		
S/N	(B) Adaptability	N	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.
6	The Firm's strategy for handling disasters	216	4.44	1.533
7	The Firm's strategy for adjusting to new market prices	216	4.71	1.292
8	The Firm's strategy for preparing alternative solutions to problems	216	4.39	1.569
9	The Firm's strategy for transiting into new processes	216	4.50	1.357
10	The Firm's proactive behaviour to market forces	216	3.93	1.922

	Aggregate Mean	4.39		
	Criterion Mean	3.50		
	(C) Flexibility	N	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.
11	The Firm's ability to be flexible with supply chain	216	3.71	1.991
12	The Firm's ability to align the firm and the business environment	216	4.47	1.407
13	The Firm's capability to cope with change and uncertainties	216	4.08	1.726
14	The firm's ability to adapt and improvise in competitive situations	216	4.66	1.295
15	The firm's ability to facilitate adaptation of organizational structures	216	4.96	1.301
	Aggregate Mean	4.38		
	Criterion Mean	3.50		

Authors' computation

and 4.38 for productivity, adaptability and flexibility respectively, which are higher than the criterion mean of 3.50. Therefore, firms under study exhibit OE.

Testing the Hypotheses

To facilitate hypotheses testing, summarized diagnostic statistics are presented first.

Table 3: Summarized Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Variable	Mean	Std Dev
DIRPAR	1.3884	.71857
ADVPAR	2.3102	.91045
ORGPRO	4.5824	1.37292
ORGADA	4.3944	1.49528
ORGFLE	4.3778	1.49525

Source: Authors' computation

Note: DIRPAR = Direct participation, ADVPAR = Advisory participation, ORGPRO = Organizational productivity, ORGADA = Organizational adaptability, ORGFLE = Organizational flexibility

In Table 4, Pearson's correlation was used to analyze the results of employees' involvement dimensions and their relationship with OE dimensions (productivity, adaptability and flexibility). Evidently, there is a strong and positive relationship between EIDM and OE dimensions as $p < 0.05$ for all the correlations hence, statistically significant.

Multicollinearity occurs when two or more predictors in the model are correlated and provide redundant information about the response variable. The test was conducted through the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance value statistics and the results are shown in Table 5. The two variables, DIRPAR and ADVPAR, had VIF value less than 10 implying no multicollinearity

Table 4: Correlation Matrix of the Variables

		DIRPAR	ADVPAR	ORGPRO	ORGADA	ORGFLE
DIRPAR	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	216				
ADVPAR	Pearson Correlation	.838**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
	N	216	216			
ORGPRO	Pearson Correlation	.507**	.856**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
	N	216	216	216		
ORGADA	Pearson Correlation	.543**	.888**	.988**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		
	N	216	216	216	216	
ORGFLE	Pearson Correlation	.551**	.893**	.978**	.989**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	216	216	216	216	216

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Source: Authors' computation

Table 5: Multicollinearity Test of Independent Variables and Collinearity diagnostics.

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
DIRPAR	.298	3.356
ADVPAR	.298	3.356

Source: Authors' computation

problem among the variables. The tolerance value checks on the degree of collinearity; where a tolerance

value lower than 0.1 shows that the variable cannot be combined as a linear combination of other independent variables. In this study, tolerance value (0.298) is greater than 0.1 indicating no case of multicollinearity for the two variables. Clearly, both tolerance value and VIF tests indicate the absence of multicollinearity in the model.

Hypotheses Results

Hypothesis One

The summary of the regression result is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Linear Regression Analysis of EIDM on Organizational Productivity.

	R2	F	α	β	t	Prob
EIDM > Org. Productivity	.54	F (1, 214) =246.28	.64	.73	13.42	0.000

Source: Authors' computation

In Table 6, organizational productivity was regressed on EIDM. It revealed that employees' participation explains a significant 54% variation in firms' organizational productivity (R2 = .54). The model fitness is confirmed by the F-statistics (F (1, 214) = 246.28, p = 0.000). The coefficient of the estimator, β , is positive and the probability value of the t-statistics which checks the significance of the estimate shows that the estimate is

significant. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected indicating that EIDM has a significant effect on organizational productivity of manufacturing firms ($\beta = .73$, t = 13.42, p<0.000).

Hypothesis Two

The summary of the regression result is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Linear Regression Analysis of EIDM on Organizational Adaptability.

	R2	F	α	β	t	Prob
EIDM > Org. Adaptability	.59	F (1, 214) = 305.94	.73	.77	17.49	0.000

Source: Authors' computation

The result in Table 7 revealed that EIDM explains a significant 59% variation in organizational adaptability (R2 = .59). The regression coefficient, β , is positive (0.77) and its t-value is statistically significant (t = 17.49, p = 0.000). The model is also well-fitted as shown by the F-statistics (F (1, 214) = 305.94, p=0.000). Evidently, employees'

involvement influence organizational adaptability in manufacturing firms.

Hypothesis Three

The regression result is summarized and presented in Table 8.

Table 7: Linear Regression Analysis of EIDM on Organizational Adaptability

	R2	F	α	β	t	Prob
EIDM > Org. Flexibility	.60	F (1, 214) = 319.61	.74	.77	17.88	0.000

Source: Authors' computation

The results in Table 8 indicate that the predictor explains 60% of the variations in organizational flexibility (R2 = .60). The F-test for model fitness (F (1, 214) = 319.61) shows the appropriateness of the model as the probability value is less than the 5% level (p=0.000). β , which is the estimate of the explanatory variable, is positive and statistically significant based on the probability value of the t-statistics (prob = 0.000) Accordingly, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, a significant positive relationship exists between the variables under study.

Saeed (2016), Dede (2019), Ezeanolue and Ezeanyim (2020), Asokk et al (2021), and Mambula et al (2021), who indicated that with employees participation, decision processes become easier, a good working environment is created; commitment, satisfaction and morale increases and the direct consequence of all these is improved productivity.

Also, the findings from testing the second hypothesis revealed that EIDM influences the organizational adaptability of manufacturing firms. This shows that when employees are part of the decision process, it will set pace for adapting to changes in the organizational dealings. This finding concurs with Ojokuku and Sajuyigbe (2014), F. F. Oyebamiji (2018) and Ugwu et al (2019), Mohsen and Sharif (2020) who reported that the extent to which employees are allowed to participate in an organizations' decision processes significantly impact on

Discussion of the Findings

The finding from the first hypothesis showed that EIDM has a significant effect on organizational productivity of manufacturing firms. Impliedly, if middle and lower level employees partake in decision making, firms' output and processes would be very effective. This finding supports

the extent to which they perceive and adjust to scenarios that take place in the organization.

Finally, the test of the third hypothesis disclosed that EIDM significantly influence organizational flexibility in manufacturing firms. This shows that a change in the involvement of middle and lower level employees in decision making in these firms would lead to a corresponding change in the firms' organizational flexibility. This is not unconnected with the fact that bringing in the employees' suggestions during decision making processes would add value to the decisions made. Hence, this will determine the extent of organizational flexibility towards considering suggestions from the employees. This finding corroborates Tizazu (2014) who stated that considering the views or opinions of employees at all levels would stimulate their attitude in the discharge of their job roles and reveal the level of flexibility in an organization, which will influence positively a firm's level of effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

This study has attempted an examination of the influence of EIDM on OE in manufacturing firms to enable the construction of new paradigm of employees' involvement. Based on the study's findings, it can be concluded that EIDM has a significant effect on organizational productivity of manufacturing firms, implying that if the middle and lower level employees partake in decisions, firms' output and processes would be more effective. The study also concluded that employees' participation influences the organizational adaptability of manufacturing firms. It is further concluded that EIDM has a significant influence on organizational flexibility which implies that bringing in the employees' suggestions during decision making processes would add value to the decisions made.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings, it is recommended that top management of manufacturing firms should see the need to constantly involve employees in their decision making processes whether directly, or through advisory involvement, if they are to continually gain more effectiveness. This study has contributed to knowledge in affirming that involving employees significantly influences a manufacturing firm's OE in terms of productivity, adaptability and flexibility.

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